

PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF BATSTATEU LEMERY EMPLOYEES AND ITS CONTRIBUTORY FACTORS: BASIS FOR HRMO PAPs

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ABSTRACT

The researcher primarily aimed to ascertain the manifested personal and professional qualities of BatStateU Lemery employees and its contributory factors. It also sought to ascertain the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, length of service. More so, it was intended to discern the effects of their personal and professional qualities to the students, colleagues/peers, and community. Lastly, it sought to propose HRMO-PAPs (Human Resource Management Office strategic programs, activities, and projects) for further personal and professional growth of the employees. This study employed descriptive method that involved the 30 employees of BatStateU Lemery at Rajah Matanda Street, Bagong Sikat, Lemery Batangas including the teaching and non-teaching personnel for First Semester, Academic Year 2019-2020. For the needed data of the study, questionnaire was made; whereas for the analysis of the data gathered, statistical tools were utilized such as: percentage, ranking, and weighted mean. In conclusion, most of the employees belonged to the age bracket of 31-40, females, married and have been in the service for 1-5 years only. Likewise, this study showed that BatStateU Lemery employees manifested the relational grace as being approachable and helpful as their most prevalent personal qualities while loyalty and integrity is their prevalent professional qualities. The main contributing factor that affects the personal and professional qualities of the employees is their mental and emotional stability. In accordance, there were observed effects of personal and professional qualities of the employees such as: willingness to gain and learn knowledge to the students; accepting and respecting one's decisions to peers or colleagues while working with school administrators and other members of the school to achieve the school vision, mission, and goals to the community. Lastly, strengthening psychological well-being of the employees was proposed that can be added in the HRMO PAPs of the university for further personal and professional growth of the employees.

Keywords: Personal and professional qualities, employees, Human Resource Management strategic plan